

Graded hexagon of opposition in fuzzy natural logic with new intermediate quantifiers

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ABSTRACT

In this article, we will form a graded hexagon of opposition as an extension of the graded Peterson's square, incorporating new variations of intermediate quantifiers. We will start with the classical Aristotle's square of opposition and its extension to hexagon. Then we introduce the graded square of opposition that was suggested by Peterson and fully formalized by the authors. We also introduce quantifiers *A few* (*A little*) and *Several* and include them in the latter. Then we introduce new forms of quantifiers and study relations of contrary, sub-contrary, contradictory and sub-(sup)-altern among them. On the basis of the knowledge of the relations among all the intermediate quantifiers we construct the graded Peterson's hexagon of opposition.

1. Introduction

1.1. Aristotle's square and hexagon of opposition

Aristotle's square of opposition is a special diagram representing relations among four basic categorical propositions. Its origin can be traced to Aristotle's tractates *On Interpretation* in the fourth century BC (see [1,2]). Aristotle himself, however, did not draw any diagram; this was done in the second century by Apuleius (see Fig. 1). It is important to emphasize that the structures of opposition were used by people interested in the esoteric sciences (magical, astrological, alchemical, or paranormal). Applications of the square of opposition in philosophical and mathematical logic, linguistic and psychology are studied in [3–5].

The categorical propositions in diagram in Fig. 1 can be formalized in predicate logic as follows:

$$*A : \text{All } B \text{ are } A \quad (\forall x)(Bx \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge (\exists x)Bx, \quad (1)$$

$$E : \text{No } B \text{ are } A \quad (\forall x)(Bx \Rightarrow \neg Ax), \quad (2)$$

$$I : \text{Some } B \text{ are } A \quad (\exists x)(Bx \wedge Ax), \quad (3)$$

$$*O : \text{Some } B \text{ are not } A \quad (\exists x)(Bx \wedge \neg Ax) \vee \neg(\exists x)Bx. \quad (4)$$

The diagonals of the square correspond to the relationship of “contradiction”. The contradictories exist between the universal affirmative **A** (“All”) and the particular negative **O** (“not all”), as well as between the universal negative **E** (“No”) and the particular

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Fig. 1. Aristotle's square of opposition.

positive I (“Some”). The relation of “*contrary*” is observed horizontally at the top between “All” and “No”. In contrast, the inverse relation, “*sub-contraries*”, holds horizontally at the bottom between “Some” and “Not all”. Finally, the vertical relation between “All” and “Some”, as well as between “No” and “Not all”, describes “*sub-altern*”. We can characterize all these relations as follows [6]:

- (i) A formula is *sub-altern* of another one, called a *super-altern* if, in any model, it must be true if its super-altern is true. At the same time, the super-altern must be false if the subaltern is false.
- (ii) We say that two formulas are *contrary* if in any model they cannot both be true, but both can be false.
- (iii) We say that two formulas are *sub-contrary* if in any model they cannot both be false, but both can be true.
- (iv) We say two formulas are *contradictory* if in any model they cannot both be true, and they cannot both be false.

Note that the Aristotle's square of opposition requires *presupposition* (existential import). This assumption is mathematically secured by adding the formula $(\exists x)Bx$. The corresponding quantifier is marked with an asterisk. Detailed explanation of the presupposition can be found in [7, Section 1]. In [8,9], the authors emphasize a significant distinction between the Aristotle's square of opposition and the “modern” square, which is based on the concepts of inner and outer negation.

Generalization of the square of opposition to a hexagon was introduced independently by three philosophers in the early 1950s: Paul Jacoby, Augustin Sesmat, and Robert Blanché (see [10–12]). Another interesting work is [13] by Nelson (translated into English [14]). The papers [15,16] by Aberdein focus on the oppositional structures in general and the hexagon of opposition in particular.

To expand the traditional square of opposition into Blanché's hexagon, we must add two new formulas, namely U and Y.¹ These formulas are introduced as the disjunction of the two top corners of the traditional square and the conjunction of the two bottom corners.

Constructing Aristotle's hexagon of opposition means defining new kinds of quantifiers that represent the top and bottom of this logical structure of opposition:

$$U = A \vee E : (\text{All or No}) B \text{ are } A \tag{5}$$

$$Y = I \wedge O : (\text{Some but Not All}) B \text{ are } A. \tag{6}$$

Then Aristotle's hexagon looks as follows:

Similarly as in the classical Aristotle's square, the basic properties between the individual quantifiers apply also in the classical hexagon. The diagonal lines in hexagon represent contradictories, where formulas A and E are contraries. Additionally, A and E together entail U, while Y entails both formulas I and O. It is intriguing to observe that the logical hexagon encompasses three of Aristotle's squares of opposition, which are AEIO, AYOU, and EYUI.

Several authors have further explored the concepts introduced in the previously mentioned works. In [18], distinctions between the Aristotle's hexagon and the *duality hexagon* are discussed. The logical hexagon, along with numerous examples and the cube of opposition is in detail described in [19]. A more intricate 3D extension of the hexagon was proposed by Moretti ([20]), Pellissier ([21]), and Smessaert ([22]).

After introduction of the concept of a fuzzy set by L.A. Zadeh in [23], a number of authors began to study generalized structures in various fields. In [19] and [24], the graded Aristotle's square of opposition is introduced, along with a cube of opposition and

¹ Blanché initially introduced Y in [17], later completing it with U in [11].

Fig. 2. Original Peterson's square of opposition.

its graded version that associates the traditional square of opposition with the dual one. The logical structures of opposition in the theory of rough set were analyzed in [25,26]. Furthermore, the gradual hexagon with fuzzy relation and the connection between the hexagon and a cube of opposition can be explored in [27].

1.2. The goals of this paper

In this paper we address the graded (Peterson's) hexagon with intermediate quantifiers as an extension of the graded Aristotle's and Peterson's squares of opposition (see [6]). We will mainly follow up on previous publications. In [28], we suggested mathematical definitions of generalized concepts of *contrary*, *contradictory*, *sub-contrary* and *sub-alterns*. The basic algebraic structure was the Łukasiewicz MV_{Δ} -algebra.

In the above-mentioned publications, we did not focus in detail on the generalized forms of intermediate quantifiers, which play an important role in human reasoning and processing of natural data, from the point of view of the newly introduced formal definition of the contradictory relation. It was this idea that led us to introduce new forms of intermediate quantifiers and study the graded Peterson hexagon of opposition.

For the reader's convenience, in Fig. 2 we present Peterson square of opposition, which was proposed as an extension of the Thompson square with the quantifiers "All", "Almost all", "Many" and "Some" (cf. [29]). Recall that the position of individual quantifiers was justified using philosophical arguments by Peterson in his book [30].

The paper is structured as follows: in Section 2, we briefly recall the basic concepts of the theories fuzzy natural logic. In Section 3, we remind generalized definitions of the relations of contrary, contradictory, sub-contrary and sub-altern. In Section 4, we introduce new intermediate quantifiers in graded Peterson's hexagon of opposition. Finally, we present several forms of graded logical hexagons with intermediate quantifiers.

2. Preliminaries

Our theory is formulated as a constituent of *fuzzy natural logic* (FNL) which consists of the following formal theories: the theory of evaluative linguistic expressions, theory of fuzzy/linguistic IF-THEN rules and inference from them, and the theory of fuzzy generalized and intermediate quantifiers. All theories are formalized using the means of higher-order fuzzy logic (fuzzy type theory; FTT) that has been in detail elaborated in [31].

2.1. Mathematical foundations

We work in Łukasiewicz fuzzy type theory L-FTT. The corresponding algebra of truth values is an MV_{Δ} -algebra $\mathcal{E} = \langle E, \vee, \wedge, \otimes, \rightarrow, \mathbf{0}, \mathbf{1}, \Delta \rangle$ where $\mathbf{0}$ is the least and $\mathbf{1}$ is the greatest element, respectively (cf., e.g., [32]). We will usually consider the Łukasiewicz one with the support $E = [0, 1]$.

The fundamental syntactical entities in L-FTT are classical and revolve around the concepts of *type* and *formula* (see [33]). Atomic types include ϵ (elements) and o (truth values). More general types are defined as follows: if α and β are types, then $(\beta\alpha)$ is a type. Types are denoted by Greek letters, the set of all types is denoted by *Types*. The set of all formulas of a given type α is denoted by $Form_{\alpha}$, the set of all formulas is *Form*.

Formulas are constructed from variables, constants (each with a specific type), and the symbol λ . Consequently, each formula *A* has a type and we write A_{α} . We often omit type if it is clear from the explanation.

Formulas in L-FTT are interpreted using the concept of a (general) frame:

$$\mathcal{M} = \langle (M_{\alpha}, \frac{\cdot}{\cdot}_{\alpha})_{\alpha \in \text{Types}}, \mathcal{E} \rangle$$

where M_α are sets of elements of type α , $\hat{=}_\alpha$ is a fuzzy equality and \mathcal{E} is an algebra of truth values. Note that $M_o = E$. Furthermore, $M_{\beta\alpha} \subseteq M_\beta^{M_\alpha}$ for all types $\beta\alpha$.²

Interpretation of a formula A_o in \mathcal{M} is a truth value $\mathcal{M}(A_o) \in E$. Furthermore, $\mathcal{M}(A_\epsilon) \in M_\epsilon$ is some element, and $\mathcal{M}(A_{\beta\alpha}) : M_\alpha \rightarrow M_\beta$ is a function.

A formal theory T of FTT is a set of formulas provable from a set of its special axioms (and, of course, also from all the logical ones). A frame \mathcal{M} is a model of T , $\mathcal{M} \models T$, if all special axioms of T are true in the degree $\mathbf{1}$, i.e., $\mathcal{M}(A_o) = \mathbf{1}$ for all axioms A_o of the theory T . A formula A_o is true in the theory T , $T \vDash A_o$, if it is true in the degree $\mathbf{1}$ in all models of T .

The following theorem is fundamental.

Theorem 1 (completeness).

- (a) A theory T is consistent iff it has a general model \mathcal{M} .
- (b) For every theory T and a formula A_o

$$T \vdash A_o \quad \text{iff} \quad T \vDash A_o.$$

In the sequel we will use special (derived) formulas Υ_{oo} and $\hat{\Upsilon}_{oo}$, using which we can express that the given formula A_o has in every model a non-zero or general (i.e., belonging to $(0, 1)$) truth value, respectively.

$$\Upsilon_{oo} \equiv \lambda z_o \cdot \neg \Delta(\neg z_o), \tag{non-zero truth value}$$

$$\hat{\Upsilon}_{oo} \equiv \lambda z_o \cdot \neg \Delta(z_o \vee \neg z_o). \tag{general truth value}$$

Note that $\mathcal{M}(\Upsilon_{oo} z_o), \mathcal{M}(\hat{\Upsilon}_{oo} z_o) \in \{0, 1\}$ in any model \mathcal{M} . We say that both formulas Υ_{oo} as well as $\hat{\Upsilon}_{oo}$ are *crisp*.

We use the following theorem in the subsequent proofs of logical syllogism validity.

Theorem 2 ([34]). Let T be a consistent theory, $A \in \text{Form}_o$ and $\mathbf{u}_{1,\alpha}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{n,\alpha}$, $\alpha \in \text{Types}$ be new special constants that do not belong to the language $J(T)$. If $T \vdash (\exists x_{1,\alpha}) \dots (\exists x_{n,\alpha}) \Delta A$ then $T \cup \{A_{x_{\alpha,1}, \dots, x_{\alpha,n}}[\mathbf{u}_{\alpha,1}, \dots, \mathbf{u}_{\alpha,n}]\}$ is a conservative extension of T .

2.2. Theory of evaluative linguistic expressions

The theory of intermediate quantifiers is rooted in the theory of evaluative linguistic expressions, which consists of special natural language expressions such as *extremely hard*, *about medium*, *roughly heavy*, *very long*, *more or less low*, *roughly robust*, *extremely bitter*, and so on. Semantics of them is formalized in the frame of special theory T^{Ev} in L-FTT. The details can be found in [34,35].

Evaluative linguistic expressions are characterized in the theory T^{Ev} by formulas

$$Sm \mathbf{v}, Me \mathbf{v}, Bi \mathbf{v}, Ze \mathbf{v} \tag{7}$$

where \mathbf{v} represents a linguistic hedge, *Sm* represents “small”, *Me* “medium”, *Bi* “big” and *Ze* represents “zero”. We use hedges “extremely” (*Ex*), “very” (*Ve*) and “significantly” (*Si*). For instance, formula *BiEx* represents the evaluative expression “extremely big”. Additionally, an *empty hedge* $\bar{\mathbf{v}}$ is consistently present in front of *small*, *medium*, and *big* if no other hedge is specified. We also consider the expression “not small” ($\neg Sm \bar{\mathbf{v}}$), “very small” (*Sm Ve*) and “significantly small” (*Sm Si*). Let us emphasize that the meaning of the negative evaluative expression $\neg Sm \bar{\mathbf{v}}$ is *not equal* to that of the antonym *Bi \bar{\mathbf{v}}*.

A special evaluative expression is “zero”. A mathematical model of its meaning in the standard context³ is

$$\tilde{Ze}_{oo} \equiv \lambda z_o \tilde{Sm} \mathbf{v}_{Ze} z_o, \tag{8}$$

Below, we introduce the evaluative expression “*positively (hedge) small*” that is formally defined by

$${}^+Sm \mathbf{v} \equiv \lambda t_o \cdot (Sm \mathbf{v})t_o \ \& \ \neg(Ze \mathbf{v}_{Ze})t_o. \tag{9}$$

Clearly, ${}^+Sm \mathbf{v} \in \text{Form}_{oo}$.

We can introduce a relation of partial ordering of hedges as follows:

$$\ll_{o(oo)(oo)} \equiv \lambda p_{oo} \lambda q_{oo} \cdot (\forall z_o) \Delta(pz \Rightarrow qz). \tag{10}$$

Theorem 3.

² If $M_{\beta\alpha} = M_\beta^{M_\alpha}$ for all types $\alpha, \beta \in \text{Types}$ then the frame is called *standard*.

³ The context is *standard* if $v_L = 0, v_S = 0.4, v_R = 1$, i.e., it is the interval $[0, 0.4] \cup [0.4, 1]$. More details about the theory of evaluative linguistic expressions can be found in [7,34] and elsewhere.

(a)

$$T^{Ev} \vdash \Delta \ll Ex \ll Si \ll Ve \ll \bar{v} \ll ML \ll Ro \ll QR \ll VR. \quad (11)$$

(b) Let $v_1 \ll v_2$ and Ev_{v_1}, Ev_{v_2} be evaluative expressions differing only in the hedges v_1, v_2 , respectively. Then

$$T^{Ev} \vdash (\forall z)(Ev_{v_1} z \Rightarrow (Ev_{v_2} z)). \quad (12)$$

Proof. (a) was proved in [37, Lemma 1].

(b) was proved in [34, Theorem 9(a)]. \square

Theorem 4.

$$T^{Ev} \vdash (\forall z)((Bi\mathbf{v})z \Rightarrow \neg(Sm\mathbf{v})z) \quad (13)$$

Proof. See [34, Theorem 8(c)]. \square

2.3. Theory of intermediate quantifiers: basic definitions

The theory of intermediate quantifiers was presented in detail in [6,36,38]. We will recall only a few most important definitions and provide the list selected intermediate quantifiers.

It is clear from the name intermediate quantifiers that this is a special group of generalized quantifiers, whose meaning lies between classical quantifiers \forall and \exists . These quantifiers quantify elements over the universe that can be a fuzzy set. The size of (fuzzy) sets is characterized using a fuzzy measure.

Definition 1. Let $R \in Form_{o(\alpha)(\alpha)}$ be a formula where $\alpha \in Types$ is an arbitrary type.

(i) A formula $\mu \in Form_{o(\alpha)(\alpha)}$ defined by

$$\mu_{o(\alpha)(\alpha)} \equiv \lambda z_{\alpha} \lambda x_{\alpha} (Rz_{\alpha})x_{\alpha} \quad (14)$$

represents a *measure on fuzzy sets* in the universe of type $\alpha \in Types$ if it has the following properties:

$$(M1) \ \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \& \Delta(y_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \& \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq y_{\alpha}) \Rightarrow ((\mu z_{\alpha})x_{\alpha} \Rightarrow (\mu z_{\alpha})y_{\alpha}),$$

$$(M2) \ \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \Rightarrow ((\mu z_{\alpha})(z_{\alpha} \setminus x_{\alpha}) \equiv \neg(\mu z_{\alpha})x_{\alpha}),$$

$$(M3) \ \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq y_{\alpha}) \& \Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \& \Delta(y_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \Rightarrow ((\mu z_{\alpha})x_{\alpha} \Rightarrow (\mu y_{\alpha})x_{\alpha})$$

where $x_{\alpha}, y_{\alpha}, z_{\alpha}$ are variables representing fuzzy sets.

(ii) The following formula characterizes *measurable fuzzy sets* of a given type α :

$$\mathbf{M}_{o(\alpha)} \equiv \lambda z_{\alpha} \cdot \neg \Delta(z_{\alpha} \equiv \emptyset_{\alpha}) \& \Delta(\mu z_{\alpha})z_{\alpha} \& (\forall x_{\alpha})(\forall y_{\alpha}) \Delta((M1) \& (M3)) \& (\forall x_{\alpha}) \Delta(M2) \quad (15)$$

where (M1)–(M3) are the axioms from (i).

Definition 2. Let $\mathcal{S} \subseteq Types$ be a selected set of types and $P = \{R \in Form_{o(\alpha)(\alpha)} \mid \alpha \in \mathcal{S}\}$ be a set of new constants. Let T be a consistent extension of the theory T^{Ev} in the language $J(T) \supseteq J^{Ev} \cup P$. We say that the theory T contains *intermediate quantifiers* w.r.t. the set of types \mathcal{S} if for all $\alpha \in \mathcal{S}$ the following is provable:

$$(i) \ T \vdash (\exists z_{\alpha}) \mathbf{M}_{o(\alpha)} z_{\alpha},$$

$$(ii) \ T \vdash (\forall z_{\alpha})(\exists x_{\alpha})(\mathbf{M}_{o(\alpha)} z_{\alpha} \Rightarrow (\Delta(x_{\alpha} \subseteq z_{\alpha}) \& \hat{Y}((\mu z_{\alpha})x_{\alpha}))).$$

We also need the operation of a *cut of a fuzzy set*. It is defined formally in [7]. In a model \mathcal{M} , it is defined as follows. Let $B = \mathcal{M}_p(y) \lesssim M_{\alpha}, Z = \mathcal{M}_p(z) \lesssim M_{\alpha}$. Then for any $m \in M_{\alpha}$

$$\mathcal{M}_p(y|z)(m) = (B|Z)(m) = \begin{cases} B(m), & \text{if } B(m) = Z(m), \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Lemma 1. Let $B, Y, Z \subseteq M$. Then

$$(a) \ [B|Z \subseteq B] = 1 \text{ and } B|Z = Z|B,^4$$

⁴ The symbol $[-]$ denotes a truth value of the expression inside. More precisely, $[B \subseteq A] = \bigwedge_{m \in M} (B(m) \Rightarrow A(m))$ where $A, B \subseteq M$.

- (b) If $[B|Y \subseteq B|Z] > 0$ then $[B|Y \subseteq B|Z] = 1$,
 (c) $B|B = B$, $B|\emptyset = \emptyset$.

Proof. (a) was proved in [37].

(b) By definition, $[B|Y \subseteq B|Z] = \bigwedge_{m \in M} ((B|Y)(m) \rightarrow (B|Z)(m))$. However, either $(B|Y)(m) = 0$ or $(B|Y)(m) = (B|Z)(m)$. In both cases $((B|Y)(m) \rightarrow (B|Z)(m)) = 1$.

(c) is obvious. \square

Definition 3. Let Ev_{oo} be a metavariable denoting a formula that represents some evaluative linguistic expression. Let $z \in Form_{o\alpha}$, $x \in Form_{\alpha}$ be variables and $A, B \in Form_{o\alpha}$ be formulas such that $T^{IQ} \vdash M_{o(\alpha)} B$, $\alpha \in \mathcal{S}$ where \mathcal{S} is a selected set of types.

- (i) An intermediate quantifier of type $\langle 1, 1 \rangle$ is one of the following formulas:

$$(Q_{Ev}^{\forall} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))], \quad (16)$$

$$(Q_{Ev}^{\exists} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\exists x)((B|z)x \wedge Ax) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))]. \quad (17)$$

- (ii) An intermediate quantifier of type $\langle 1, 1 \rangle$ with the presupposition (existential import) is one of the following formulas:

$$(*Q_{Ev}^{\forall} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\exists x)((B|z)x \& (\forall x)((B|z)x \Rightarrow Ax)) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))], \quad (18)$$

$$(*Q_{Ev}^{\exists} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists z)[(\neg(\exists x)(B|z)x \nabla ((\exists x)((B|z)x \wedge Ax)) \wedge Ev((\mu B)(B|z))]. \quad (19)$$

The formula $B \in Form_{o\alpha}$ represents a *universe of quantification*.

In the sequel, we will denote the theory due to Definitions 2 and 3 by T^{IQ} and fix a selected set of types \mathcal{S} .
 Either of the quantifiers (16)–(19) construes the sentence

$\langle \text{Quantifier} \rangle B$'s are A .

Let \mathcal{M} be a model, α a type and $B, Z, A \subseteq M_{\alpha}$ be fuzzy sets. Let $F_{Ev}^R(B, B|Z) = \mathcal{M}(Ev(\mu(B, B|Z)))$ be evaluation of a *measure of the size of the Z-part of B*. Then the truth value of formula (16) is computed as follows:

$$\mathcal{M}((Q_{Ev}^{\forall} x)(B, A)) = \bigvee \left\{ \bigwedge_{m \in M} ((B|Z)(m) \rightarrow A(m)) \wedge F_{Ev}^R(B, B|Z) \mid Z \subseteq M, B|Z \neq \emptyset \right\}. \quad (20)$$

Note that we exclude the possibility that $B|Z = \emptyset$ since no quantifier considered above allows empty set as a universe of quantification.

Definition 4. The following intermediate quantifiers can be defined using specific evaluative linguistic expressions after replacing Ev in (16)–(19):

A: All B are $A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\forall} x)(B, A) \equiv (\forall x)(Bx \Rightarrow Ax)$,

E: No B are $A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A) \equiv (\forall x)(Bx \Rightarrow \neg Ax)$,

P: Almost all B are $A := (Q_{BiEx}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$,

B: Almost all B are not $A := (Q_{BiEx}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$,

T: Most B are $A := (Q_{BiVe}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$,

D: Most B are not $A := (Q_{BiVe}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$,

K: Many B are $A := (Q_{-Sm}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$,

G: Many B are not $A := (Q_{-Sm}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$,

S: Several B are $A := (Q_{-SmVe}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$,

Z: Several B are not $A := (Q_{-SmVe}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$,

F: A few (A little) B are $A := (Q_{-SmSi}^{\forall} x)(B, A)$,

V: A few (A little) B are not $A := (Q_{-SmSi}^{\forall} x)(B, \neg A)$,

I: Some B are $A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\exists} x)(B, A) \equiv (\exists x)(Bx \wedge Ax)$,

O: Some B are not $A := (Q_{Bi\Delta}^{\exists} x)(B, \neg A) \equiv (\exists x)(Bx \wedge \neg Ax)$.

2.4. The quantifiers “A few”, “Several” and “A little bit”

In [39] we defined the quantifiers “A few” and “Several” using the evaluative expression ${}^+Sm\mathbf{v}$. However, it turned out that such a definition is non-satisfactory. The reason is impossibility to distinguish between both quantifiers. Recall that according to Merriam-Webster dictionary, the meaning of “A few” or “Several” indicates more than one or two, but less than “Many”. Moreover, “Several” means larger quantity than “A few”; namely “Several” means 3-4 (at least) and “A few” means 1-2 (or more). Hence, “Several” implies “A few”. To assure such behavior, we must modify the definition given in [39]. Namely, we must change the used evaluative expressions $SmSi$ and $SmVe$ into their negations, as is done in Definition 4 for the quantifiers (S), (Z), (F) and (V).⁵

The following theorem was proved in [40]. It implies that if we consider ordinary sets then the computation of the truth value (18) is significantly simplified.

Theorem 5. *Let \mathcal{M} be a model and A, B, M be nonempty sets of some type α . Let $B, A \subseteq M$. Then the truth value of the quantifier (20) is equal to*

$$\mathcal{M}((Q_{Ev}^{\forall, x})(B, A)) = F_{Ev}^R(B, B \cap A). \quad (21)$$

For example, let M be a set of various kinds of fruits and B a set of pears where $|B| = 20$. Let $A \subseteq B$ be a set of green pears. The following table contains truth values of two quantifiers computed using (21) for various numbers of green pears.

$ A $	“A few”	“Several”
1	0.1	0.01
2	0.8	0.4
3	1	0.8
4	1	1

However, there exists also another relation that can informally be characterized as “big (fuzzy) sets contain small ones”. For quantifiers defined using evaluative expressions $Bi\mathbf{v}$ this works in accordance with the sub-altern relation. For example, “Most” implies “Many” (i.e., $\mathbf{T} \Rightarrow \mathbf{K}$) and also, a (fuzzy) set containing most elements of the universe has a subset containing many elements of it.

When considering fuzzy sets over a universe with a limited number of elements (e.g., 3–6) then it is possible to identify (fuzzy) sets with sufficiently large measure but simultaneously identifying (fuzzy) sets with significantly small measure becomes challenging. This may not be always true since it depends on the context (i.e., on a given model). For instance, if we examine a set with 4 elements, a set with 2 elements may have a standard measure of 0.5, indicating it as “not small”, while a singleton has a measure of 0.25, which can hardly be deemed “significantly small”. In other words, we may hardly define “a few” elements inside it.

To avoid the above difficulties, we introduce two properties which assert that within a given fuzzy set $z|y$, there exists a notably small yet non-empty fuzzy set $z|s$ (w.r.t. the size of fuzzy sets measured using the measure μ):

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{NSQ}_{\alpha(\alpha\alpha)} &\equiv \lambda z_{\alpha\alpha} \cdot (\forall y_{\alpha\alpha})(\exists s_{\alpha\alpha})\Delta[\neg Sm\bar{\mathbf{v}}((\mu z)(z|y)) \Rightarrow \\ &(z|s) \subseteq (z|y) \& {}^+SmSi((\mu z)(z|s))], \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{PSQ}_{\alpha(\alpha\alpha)} &\equiv \lambda z_{\alpha\alpha} \cdot (\forall y_{\alpha\alpha})(\exists s_{\alpha\alpha})\Delta[Sm\bar{\mathbf{v}}((\mu z)(z|y)) \Rightarrow \\ &(z|s) \subseteq (z|y) \& {}^+SmSi((\mu z)(z|s))]. \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

The property **NSQ** assures existence of a significantly small fuzzy subset inside a non-small fuzzy set and **PSQ** assures the same for small fuzzy sets. While such properties are intuitively reasonable, they do not imply from the axioms of measure. Therefore, we cannot adopt (22) or (23) as axioms universally valid for all fuzzy sets $z_{\alpha\alpha}$.

In the rest of this paper, by T we denote some consistent extension of the theory T^{IQ} in which axiom (22) or (23) holds for any universe of quantification. Eventually, we will also assume that T contains regular fuzzy sets in the sense of [7, Definition 7].

Lemma 2.

(a) *Let $T \vdash \mathbf{NSQ} B_{\alpha\alpha}$ and $\mathbf{v} \in \{Ex, Si, Ve, \bar{\mathbf{v}}\}$. Then*

$$T \vdash (\forall y_{\alpha\alpha})(\exists s_{\alpha\alpha})\Delta[Bi\mathbf{v}((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow (B|s) \subseteq (B|y) \& {}^+SmSi((\mu B)(B|s))] \quad (24)$$

⁵ In our framework, we understand size of (fuzzy) sets through the concept of measure, which includes both countable and uncountable aspects, making “A few” and “A little” formally indistinguishable.

Fig. 3. Extensions of selected evaluative expressions.

(b) Let $T \vdash \text{PSQ } B_{o\alpha}$ and $\nu \in \{Ve, \bar{\nu}\}$. Then

$$T \vdash (\forall y_{o\alpha})(\exists s_{o\alpha}) \Delta [Sm \nu((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow (B|s) \subseteq (B|y) \& {}^+ Sm Si((\mu B)(B|s))] \tag{25}$$

Proof. (a) Using substitution in axiom (22) we can extend conservatively the theory T by a new constant $u_{o\alpha}$ and obtain

$$T \vdash \neg Sm \nu((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow (B|u_{o\alpha}) \subseteq (B|y) \& {}^+ Sm Si((\mu B)(B|u_{o\alpha})). \tag{26}$$

Using Theorem 4 we have

$$T \vdash Bi \nu((\mu B)(B|y)) \Rightarrow \neg Sm \bar{\nu}((\mu B)(B|y)). \tag{27}$$

Joining (26), (27) and using properties of FTT, we obtain (24).

(b) is proved analogously using Theorem 3(b). \square

Theorem 6. Let T be consistent theory in which axiom PSQ holds true and let \mathcal{M} be a model of T . Let $T \vdash (Q_{\neg Sm Ve}^{\nu} x_{\alpha})(B_{o\alpha}, A_{o\alpha})$ and denote $B = \mathcal{M}(B_{o\alpha}), A = \mathcal{M}(A_{o\alpha}) \subseteq M_{\alpha}$. Then there are fuzzy sets $Y, S \subseteq M_{\alpha}$ such that $F_{\neg Sm Ve}^R(B, B|Y) > 0$, $B|S \subseteq B|Y$ and

$$F_{+ Sm Si}^R(B, B|S) > 0.$$

Proof. Using substitution axiom, it follows from the assumption that

$$\mathcal{M}((\exists y)((\forall x)(B|y)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge \neg Sm Ve(\mu B)(B|y)) = 1$$

which is interpreted in \mathcal{M} as

$$\bigvee_{Y \subseteq M_{\alpha}} \left(\bigwedge_{m \in M_{\alpha}} ((B|Y)(m) \rightarrow A(m)) \wedge F_{\neg Sm Ve}^R(B, B|Y) \right) = 1.$$

Hence, there is a fuzzy set $Y_0 \subseteq M_{\alpha}$ such that

$$F_{\neg Sm Ve}^R(B, B|Y_0) > 0 \tag{28}$$

(note that the truth value in (28) can be very close to 1). Joining (28) with the interpretation of axiom (23) we conclude that there is a fuzzy set $S \subseteq M_{\alpha}$ such that

$$0 < [B|S \subseteq B|Y_0] \otimes F_{+ Sm Si}^R(B, B|S).$$

Using Lemma 1(b) we obtain the theorem. \square

This theorem justifies formally the following: if the quantifier ‘‘Several B are A ’’ is true then there is a model \mathcal{M} and a fuzzy subset S of B of elements of type α that contains *very few* (*very little, a little bit*) elements having the property A . Theorem 5 assures us that such a model indeed exists. Namely, we may consider a special case $B, A \subseteq \mathbb{R} = M_{\alpha}$ such that $F_{+ Sm Si}^R(B, B \cap A) = 1$, i.e., that the quantifier ‘‘A little bit of B is A ’’ is true in the degree 1 (cf. Fig. 3). The results of this section will be applied in the sequel in construction of the graded square and hexagon of opposition.

3. Graded Aristotle’s square and hexagon of opposition

3.1. Basic definitions

We will first recall definition of the relations forming the graded Aristotle’s square and hexagon of opposition.

Fig. 4. Graded Aristotle's square of opposition, contradiction is based on the Δ operation.

Definition 5. Let T be a consistent theory of \mathbb{L} -FTT, $\mathcal{M} \models T$ be its model and $P_1, P_2 \in Form_o$ be closed formulas of type o .

(i) A formula P_2 is a *subaltern* of P_1 and a formula P_1 is a *superaltern* of P_2 in the model \mathcal{M} if

$$\mathcal{M}(P_1) \leq \mathcal{M}(P_2). \tag{29}$$

It is *subaltern in the theory T* if $T \vdash P_1 \Rightarrow P_2$. By completeness, this means that inequality (29) holds true in every model $\mathcal{M} \models T$.

(ii) P_1 and P_2 are *contraries* in the model \mathcal{M} if

$$\mathcal{M}(P_1) \otimes \mathcal{M}(P_2) = 0. \tag{30}$$

They are *contraries in the theory T* if $T \vdash \neg(P_1 \& P_2)$. By completeness, this is equivalent to (30) for every model $\mathcal{M} \models T$.

(iii) P_1 and P_2 are *sub-contraries* in the model \mathcal{M} if

$$\mathcal{M}(P_1) \oplus \mathcal{M}(P_2) = 1. \tag{31}$$

They are *sub-contraries in the theory T* if $T \vdash (P_1 \vee P_2)$. By completeness, this is equivalent to (31) for every model $\mathcal{M} \models T$.

(iv) P_1 and P_2 are *contradictories* in the model \mathcal{M} if both

$$\mathcal{M}(P_1) \otimes \mathcal{M}(P_2) = 0 \text{ as well as } \mathcal{M}(P_1) \oplus \mathcal{M}(P_2) = 1. \tag{32}$$

They are *contradictories in the theory T* if both $T \vdash P_1 \& P_2 \equiv \perp$ as well as $T \vdash P_1 \vee P_2$. By completeness, this is equivalent to (32) for every model $\mathcal{M} \models T$.

Remark 1. In [6], we defined the relation of contradictory using the Δ operation: namely, P_1 and P_2 are *contradictories in a model \mathcal{M}* if both $\mathcal{M}_p(\Delta P_1) \otimes \mathcal{M}_p(\Delta P_2) = 0$ as well as $\mathcal{M}_p(\Delta P_1) \oplus \mathcal{M}_p(\Delta P_2) = 1$ hold. This definition, however, is inconvenient since such definition of *contradictory* relation allows positive universal quantifier as well as negative particular quantifier to be true in “high degrees”; see Fig. 4. Our modified Definition 5(iv) from [41] is more natural as will be seen below on the generalized Blanché hexagon in which a new definition of the contradictory relation is used.

Lemma 3. Let $B, A \in Form_{o\alpha}$, $x \in Form_\alpha$ be formulas. Then the following is provable:

- (a) $T \vdash (\mathbf{S}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{F})$,
- (b) $T \vdash (\mathbf{K}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{S})$,
- (c) $T \vdash (\mathbf{Z}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{V})$,
- (d) $T \vdash (\mathbf{G}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{Z})$.

Proof. (a) After rewriting, the proposition says that

$$T \vdash (\exists y)[(\forall x)((B|y)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge \neg SmVe((\mu B)(B|y))] \Rightarrow (\exists y')[(\forall x)((B|y')x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge \neg SmSi((\mu B)(B|y'))] \tag{33}$$

where $y, y' \in Form_{o\alpha}$, $x \in Form_\alpha$. From Theorem 3(b), we obtain

$$T^{Ev} \vdash (\forall z_o)((SmSi)z \Rightarrow (SmVe)z).$$

Then (a) follows from this and (33) using contraposition.

(b) After rewriting, the proposition says that

$$T \vdash (\exists y)[(\forall x)((B|y)x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge \neg Sm\bar{v}((\mu B)(B|y))] \Rightarrow (\exists y')[(\forall x)((B|y')x \Rightarrow Ax) \wedge \neg SmVe((\mu B)(B|y'))] \tag{34}$$

where $y, y' \in Form_{o\alpha}$, $x \in Form_\alpha$. Then, similarly as above, from $T^{Ev} \vdash (\forall z_o)((SmVe)z \Rightarrow (Sm\bar{v})z)$ we obtain (34) using contraposition.

(c)–(d) are proved analogously. \square

Fig. 5. Graded hexagon of opposition based on contradictory relation due Definition 5.

The following theorem summarizes the relations of superaltern (subaltern) between selected intermediate quantifiers.

Theorem 7 ([36] and Lemma 3). *Let T be a consistent extension of T^{Ev} . Then the following implications are provable:*

- (a) $T \vdash (A) \Rightarrow (P), T \vdash (P) \Rightarrow (T), T \vdash (T) \Rightarrow (K), T \vdash (K) \Rightarrow (S), T \vdash (S) \Rightarrow (F)$.
- (b) $T \vdash (*A) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*P) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*T) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*K) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*S) \Rightarrow (I), T \vdash (*F) \Rightarrow (I)$.
- (c) $T \vdash (E) \Rightarrow (B), T \vdash (B) \Rightarrow (D), T \vdash (D) \Rightarrow (G), T \vdash (G) \Rightarrow (Z), T \vdash (Z) \Rightarrow (V)$.
- (d) $T \vdash (*E) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*B) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*D) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*G) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*Z) \Rightarrow (O), T \vdash (*V) \Rightarrow (O)$.

In the theorem below we list all the properties that form the graded Aristotle’s square of opposition. All the formal proofs of properties can be found in [41]. Let us recall at this point that the syntactic proofs of the properties listed below, which were constructed in [41] will be used in formal proofs in the next part of this publication.

Theorem 8. *In the graded square of opposition AEIO the following properties hold:*

- (a) *Formulas $*A, O$ and $*E, I$ are contradictories in T^{IQ} .*
- (b) *Formulas $*A$ and E are contraries in T^{IQ} .*
- (c) *Formulas $*I$ and O are sub-contraries in T^{IQ} .*
- (d) *Formula $*A$ is superaltern of the formula I and $*E$ is superaltern of the formula O in T^{IQ} .*

3.2. Graded Aristotle’s hexagon

Generalizing the graded Aristotle’s square to the graded Aristotelian hexagon involves definition of formulas that represent top and bottom:

$$U := A \vee E \quad \text{All or No } B \text{ are } A. \tag{35}$$

$$Y := I \& O \quad \text{Some but Not All } B \text{ are } A. \tag{36}$$

Definition 6. Let A, E, I, O, U, Y be six sentences. We call the tuple (A, E, I, O, U, Y) a graded hexagon of opposition if and only if the following relations among the six sentences hold:

- (a) A, E, I, O is the graded Aristotle’s square of opposition.
- (b) $U = A \vee E$.
- (c) $Y = I \& O$.
- (d) The formulas Y and U are contradictories in T^{IQ} due to Definition 5.

Remark 2. At this point it is important to explain the reason for the introduction of the contradictory relation between the formulas U and Y . There are several approaches and interpretations of the classic and generalized hexagon of opposition. There are publications from the areas modal logic, rough sets, probabilistic theory, formal concept analysis, etc. (see [17,42–44]). The reason for the assumption of the contradictory relation between U and Y is related to the assumption of the formulas A and O , where it does not apply in our approach that $\neg A \neq O$. For the details see [6, Subsection 4.2].

Theorem 9. *Every graded logical hexagon forms three graded squares of opposition AEIO, AYOU and EYIU based on the relations due to Definition 5.*

Proof. Proofs of all the properties of can be found in [41,45]. \square

Comparing Fig. 5 with Fig. 4 one can see that Definition 5(iv) of contradictory is more natural than the original definition with the Δ operation. Observe, that the universal positive and particular negative quantifiers can not be both true in “big” truth degrees.

Fig. 6. Graded Peterson's square of opposition including "A few" and "Several".

4. Graded Peterson's hexagon as an extension of the graded Aristotle's square

In this section, we will mention the graded Peterson square of opposition extended by the quantifiers "A few" and "Several" and then its extension to the graded hexagon. Our results both syntactic and semantic using the construction of finite models were analyzed in [6,46]. All the properties that depicted graphically have been syntactically proven in [37,45].

4.1. Discussion about the position of "small" and "large" quantifiers

In general, Peterson's square of opposition contains quantifiers that can be called "small" and "large", which, by their meaning and position in the square, divide the square into upper and lower halves.

The imaginary interface in our approach is characterized by the quantifier "Many" (see [7]) $(Q_{\neg Sm \bar{v}}^{\forall})(B, A)$. We demonstrated that there is a model in which $(Q_{\neg Sm \bar{v}}^{\forall})(B, A)$ and $(Q_{\neg Sm \bar{v}}^{\forall})(B, \neg A)$ are in the relation of contrary, and also a model in which they are sub-contrary.

Quantifiers that stand above the quantifier "Many" (see Fig. 6) are defined using the evaluative linguistic expressions *BiEx*, *BiVe*, etc. Thus, the quantifier "Almost all" takes into account a larger (fuzzy) set (in the sense of measure) than the quantifier "Most" based on "very big". Using the sub-altern relation, the quantifier "Most" can be true to a greater degree than the quantifier "Almost all".

The opposite is the case with "smaller" quantifiers, which in meaning are below the quantifier "Many". Recall that the quantifier "A few" refers to a smaller (fuzzy) set than "Several" and, therefore, the quantifier "Several" must be placed above "A few" in the graded Peterson's square, i.e., "A few" is a subaltern of "Several". Let us emphasize that the relation sup-sub-altern is the relation between two *truth values* of the respective quantifiers.

4.2. Graded Peterson's hexagon

The graded hexagon of opposition extends the repertoire of expressions that can be formally construed. For example:

A few seniors are vaccinated against the flu and a few seniors are not.

Definition 7. The following are new intermediate quantifiers:

$$U_{BiEx} := P \vee B \quad (\text{Almost all } B \text{ are } A) \text{ or } (\text{Almost all } B \text{ are not } A), \tag{37}$$

$$U_{BiVe} := T \vee D \quad (\text{Most } B \text{ are } A) \text{ or } (\text{Most } B \text{ are not } A), \tag{38}$$

$$Y_{\neg Sm \bar{v}} := K \& G \quad (\text{Many } B \text{ are } A) \text{ and } (\text{Many } B \text{ are not } A), \tag{39}$$

$$Y_{\neg Sm Ve} := S \& Z \quad (\text{Several } B \text{ are } A) \text{ and } (\text{Several } B \text{ are not } A), \tag{40}$$

$$Y_{\neg Sm Si} := F \& V \quad (\text{A few } B \text{ are } A) \text{ and } (\text{A few } B \text{ are not } A). \tag{41}$$

In case we need to consider quantifiers with the presupposition, we will add the asterisk: $*U_{BiEx}$, $*U_{BiVe}$, $*Y_{\neg Sm \bar{v}}$, $*Y_{\neg Sm Ve}$, $*Y_{\neg Sm Si}$.

4.3. Relations among new intermediate quantifiers

In this subsection, we formally prove relations among new intermediate quantifiers. We will also refer to results that have already been established and are closely linked to the construction of the graded hexagon. It is important to note that all the relations that form the graded Peterson's square were proved in the earlier publications [6,37].

4.3.1. Contraries

In the proof of the lemma below, the main property that plays an important role for the construction of syntactic proofs is the property of monotonicity of positive and negative quantifiers.

Lemma 4. *The following is provable:*

- (a) $T^{IQ} \vdash \neg(*\mathbf{A} \& *Y_{\neg Sm Ve}), T^{IQ} \vdash \neg(*\mathbf{A} \& *Y_{\neg Sm Si}), T^{IQ} \vdash \neg(*\mathbf{A} \& *Y_{\neg Sm v})$.
 (b) $T^{IQ} \vdash \neg(*\mathbf{E} \& *Y_{\neg Sm Ve}), T^{IQ} \vdash \neg(*\mathbf{E} \& *Y_{\neg Sm Si}), T^{IQ} \vdash \neg(*\mathbf{E} \& *Y_{\neg Sm v})$.

Proof. ad) (a) Using $T^{IQ} \vdash *\mathbf{A} \& \mathbf{O} \Rightarrow \perp$ from [41, Lemma 2(a)] and by weakening with **I** we have that

$$T^{IQ} \vdash *\mathbf{A} \& (\mathbf{I} \& \mathbf{O}) \Rightarrow \perp. \quad (42)$$

Then from graded Peterson's square we have that $T^{IQ} \vdash *\mathbf{S} \Rightarrow \mathbf{I}$ and $T^{IQ} \vdash *\mathbf{Z} \Rightarrow \mathbf{O}$. Hence we have $T^{IQ} \vdash *\mathbf{S} \& *\mathbf{Z} \Rightarrow \mathbf{I} \& \mathbf{O}$. From this we have

$$T^{IQ} \vdash *\mathbf{A} \& (*\mathbf{S} \& *\mathbf{Z}) \Rightarrow *\mathbf{A} \& (\mathbf{I} \& \mathbf{O}). \quad (43)$$

Finally, from (42) and (43) using transitivity we obtain

$$T^{IQ} \vdash (*\mathbf{A} \& *Y_{\neg Sm Ve}) \Rightarrow \perp.$$

(b) can be proved analogously. \square

Theorem 10. *The following holds true:*

- (a) *Formulas $*\mathbf{A}$ and $*Y_{\neg Sm Ve}$ are contraries in T^{IQ} .*
 (b) *Formulas $*\mathbf{A}$ and $*Y_{\neg Sm Si}$ are contraries in T^{IQ} .*
 (c) *Formulas $*\mathbf{A}$ and $*Y_{\neg Sm v}$ are contraries in T^{IQ} .*
 (d) *Formulas $*\mathbf{E}$ and $*Y_{\neg Sm Ve}$ are contraries in T^{IQ} .*
 (e) *Formulas $*\mathbf{E}$ and $*Y_{\neg Sm Si}$ are contraries in T^{IQ} .*
 (f) *Formulas $*\mathbf{E}$ and $*Y_{\neg Sm v}$ are contraries in T^{IQ} .*

Proof. This follows from Lemma 4. \square

In Fig. 7, we graphically present the valid contraries between quantifiers (dashed lines) that we proved in Theorem 10. We also present a property of contrary between classical quantifiers. For example we can observe that the universal quantifier “All B are A ” is contrary with quantifier “Few B are A and Few B are not A ”.

4.3.2. Sub-alterns and superalterns

Lemma 5. *The following is provable:*

- (a) $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{U} \Rightarrow \mathbf{U}_{BiEx}, T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{U}_{BiEx} \Rightarrow \mathbf{U}_{BiVe}$.
 (b) $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm v} \Rightarrow \mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm Ve}, T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm Ve} \Rightarrow \mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm Si}, T^{IQ} \vdash *\mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm Si} \Rightarrow \mathbf{Y}$.

Proof. ad) (a) By the monotonicity of **A** and **P** (i.e. $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{A} \Rightarrow \mathbf{P}$) as well as of **E** and **B** (i.e. $T^{IQ} \vdash \mathbf{E} \Rightarrow \mathbf{B}$) and using properties of L-FTT we obtain $T^{IQ} \vdash (\mathbf{A} \vee \mathbf{E}) \Rightarrow (\mathbf{P} \vee \mathbf{B})$.

ad) (b) Analogously as (a) applying weakening of $\&$. \square

Theorem 11. *The following holds true:*

- (a) *The formula \mathbf{U} is superaltern of \mathbf{U}_{BiEx} .*
 (b) *The formula \mathbf{U}_{BiEx} is superaltern of \mathbf{U}_{BiVe} .*
 (c) *The formula $\mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm Ve}$ is sub-altern of $\mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm v}$.*
 (d) *The formula $\mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm Si}$ is sub-altern of $\mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm Ve}$.*
 (e) *The formula \mathbf{Y} is sub-altern of $\mathbf{Y}_{\neg Sm Si}$.*

Proof. This is a consequence of Lemma 5. \square

Lemma 6. *The following is provable:*

Fig. 8. The relation of sub-altern.

(b) The formulas **P** and **B** are superalterns of U_{BiVe} .

Proof. It is consequence of the Lemma 7. \square

Lemma 8. The following formulas are provable in T^{IQ} :

- (a) $T^{IQ} \vdash Y_{\neg Sm\bar{v}} \Rightarrow S$; $T^{IQ} \vdash Y_{\neg Sm\bar{v}} \Rightarrow Z$.
- (b) $T^{IQ} \vdash Y_{\neg Sm\bar{v}} \Rightarrow F$; $T^{IQ} \vdash Y_{\neg Sm\bar{v}} \Rightarrow V$.
- (c) $T^{IQ} \vdash *Y_{\neg Sm\bar{v}} \Rightarrow I$; $T^{IQ} \vdash *Y_{\neg Sm\bar{v}} \Rightarrow O$.
- (d) $T^{IQ} \vdash Y_{\neg SmVe} \Rightarrow F$; $T^{IQ} \vdash Y_{\neg SmVe} \Rightarrow V$.
- (e) $T^{IQ} \vdash *Y_{\neg SmVe} \Rightarrow I$; $T^{IQ} \vdash *Y_{\neg SmVe} \Rightarrow O$.
- (e) $T^{IQ} \vdash *Y_{\neg SmSi} \Rightarrow I$; $T^{IQ} \vdash *Y_{\neg SmSi} \Rightarrow O$.

Proof. It is a consequence of the $T^{IQ} \vdash (Ax \& Bx) \Rightarrow Bx$, by transitivity and monotonicity of quantifiers. \square

Theorem 14. The following is true:

- (a) Formulas **S**, **Z**, **F**, **V**, **I**, **O** are sub-alterns of $Y_{\neg Sm\bar{v}}$.
- (b) Formulas **F**, **V**, **I**, **O** are sub-alterns of $Y_{\neg SmVe}$.
- (d) Formulas **I**, **O** are sub-alterns of $Y_{\neg SmSi}$.

Proof. It is consequence of the Lemma 8. \square

In Fig. 8, we present a graphical representation of the proven properties of subaltern and superaltern between quantifiers. For example the quantifier “Several B are A and Several B are not A ” is superlatern of the quantifier “Many B are A ” as well as of the quantifier “Many B are not A ”.

Fig. 9. Example of the graded Peterson's hexagon of opposition with "A few" and "Several".

4.3.3. Sub-contrary

Lemma 9. The following is provable:

- (a) $T^{IQ} \vdash *I \nabla U_{BiEx}, T^{IQ} \vdash *I \nabla U_{BiVe}$
- (b) $T^{IQ} \vdash *O \nabla U_{BiEx}, T^{IQ} \vdash *O \nabla U_{BiVe}$

Proof. ad (a) From Lemma 5(a) and by general properties of L-FTT we obtain $T^{IQ} \vdash (*I \nabla U) \Rightarrow (*I \nabla U_{ExBi})$. By Theorem 7(b) from [41] and using the rule of modus ponens we obtain the first property. The second property can be proved by Lemma (a) from [41].

ad (b) Analogously as (a) by Theorem 7(a) from [41]. \square

Theorem 15. Formulas $*I$ and $*O$ are sub-contraries with each of U_{BiEx}, U_{BiVe} , respectively.

Proof. It is a consequence of Lemma 9. \square

In Fig. 7, we graphically present a valid property of sub-contrary between quantifiers (dotted lines) proved in Theorem 15. In addition, we present a valid sub-contrary property between classical quantifiers. We present generalization of two triangles from the classical hexagon of opposition in Fig. 7. Finally, in Fig. 9 we present an example of the graded Peterson's logical hexagon of opposition in a specific model.

5. Conclusion

In this article, we continue the study of fuzzy intermediate quantifiers in connection with their position in the graded Peterson's hexagon of opposition. We also introduced a new mathematical definition of the contradictory relation, which, as we have shown in the examples, leads to a more natural behavior of the graded Aristotle's as well as graded Peterson's hexagon of opposition.

In the second half of the publication, we devoted ourselves to the introduction of new forms of fuzzy intermediate quantifiers and their position in graded Peterson's hexagon of opposition. Another goal was to expand the Peterson's cube of opposition. Further

research will be focused on the “small” quantifiers “A few”, “Several” and “Not many”, which have specific position due to the monotonicity and on the related logical syllogisms.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petra Murinová: Writing – original draft. **Karel Fiala:** Validation. **Stefania Boffa:** Validation. **Vilém Novák:** Validation, Formal analysis.

Declaration of competing interest

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Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] Wikipedia, <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/aristotle>, 2004.
- [2] T. Parsons, *The Square of Opposition in Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, First published 1997, substantive revision 2006, 2006.
- [3] J. Béziau, K. Gan-Krzywoszyńska, *Handbook of abstracts of the 2nd World Congress on the Square of Opposition*, Corte, Corsica, June 2010, pp. 17–20.
- [4] J. Béziau, K. Gan-Krzywoszyńska, *Handbook of abstracts of the 3rd World Congress on the Square of Opposition*, Beirut, Lebanon, June 26–30, 2010.
- [5] J. Béziau, K. Gan-Krzywoszyńska, *Handbook of abstracts of the 4th World Congress on the Square of Opposition*, Roma, Vatican, May 5–9, 2014, pp. 26–30.
- [6] P. Murinová, V. Novák, Analysis of generalized square of opposition with intermediate quantifiers, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 242 (2014) 89–113.
- [7] P. Murinová, V. Novák, The theory of intermediate quantifiers in fuzzy natural logic revisited and the model of “many”, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 388 (2020) 56–89.
- [8] S. Peters, D. Westerståhl, *Quantifiers in Language and Logic*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 2006.
- [9] D. Westerståhl, The traditional square of opposition and generalized quantifiers, *Stud. Log.* 2 (2008) 1–18.
- [10] P. Jacoby, A triangle of opposites for types of propositions in Aristotelian logic, *New Scholast.* 24 (1) (1950) 32–56.
- [11] R. Blanché, Sur l’opposition des concepts, *Theoria* 19 (1953) 89–130.
- [12] A. Sesmat, *Logique II: Les raisonnements, la logique, Hermann*, 1951.
- [13] L. Nelson, *Typische Denkfehler in der Philosophie: Nachschrift der Vorlesung vom Sommersemester 1921*, vol. 623, Felix Meiner Verlag, 2011.
- [14] L. Nelson, *A Theory of Philosophical Fallacies*, Springer, 2016.
- [15] A. Aberdein, Book review - Leonard Nelson: a theory of philosophical fallacies, *Argumentation* 31 (2) (2017) 455–461.
- [16] A. Aberdein, Nelson’s logical diagrams, *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.06498*, 2023.
- [17] R. Blanché, Quantity, modality, and other kindred systems of categories, *Mind* LXI 243 (1952) 369–375.
- [18] H. Smessaert, The classical Aristotelian hexagon versus the modern duality hexagon, *Log. Univers.* 6 (2012) 171–199.
- [19] D. Dubois, H. Prade, From blanché’s hexagonal organization of concepts to formal concept analysis and possibility theory, *Log. Univers.* 6 (2012) 149–169.
- [20] A. Moretti, The geometry of logical oppositions and the opposition of logic to it, in: I. Bianchi, U. Savardi (Eds.), *The Perception and Cognition of Contraries*, 2009, pp. 20–60.
- [21] R. Pellissier, “setting” n-opposition, *Log. Univers.* 2 (2) (2008) 235–263.
- [22] H. Smessaert, On the 3d-visualisation of logical relations, *Log. Univers.* 3 (2) (2009) 303–332.
- [23] L.A. Zadeh, Fuzzy sets, *Inf. Control* 8 (1965) 338–353.
- [24] D. Dubois, H. Prade, Gradual structures of oppositions, in: F. Esteva, L. Magdalena, J.L. Verdegay (Eds.), *Enric Trillas: Passion for Fuzzy Sets*, in: *Studies in Fuzziness and Soft Computing*, vol. 322, 2015, pp. 79–91.
- [25] D. Ciucci, D. Dubois, H. Prade, Oppositions in rough set theory, in: T. Li, H.S. Nguyen, G. Wang, J.W. Grzymala-Busse, R. Janicki, A.E. Hassanien, H. Yu (Eds.), *Proc. 7th Int. Conf. on Rough Sets and Knowledge Technology (RSKT12)*, Chengdu, Aug. 17–20, in: LNCS, vol. 7414, 2012, pp. 504–513.
- [26] D. Ciucci, D. Dubois, H. Prade, The structure of oppositions in rough set theory and formal concept analysis - toward a new bridge between the two settings, in: C. Beierle, C. Meghini (Eds.), *Proc. 8th Int. Symp. on Foundations of Information and Knowledge Systems (FoIKS14)*, Bordeaux, Mar. 3–7, in: LNCS, vol. 8367, 2014, pp. 154–173.
- [27] D. Ciucci, D. Dubois, H. Prade, Structures of opposition induced by relations: the Boolean and the gradual cases, *Ann. Math. Artif. Intell.* (2016), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10472--015--9480--8>.
- [28] P. Murinová, V. Novák, Graded generalized hexagon in fuzzy natural logic, in: *Information Processing and Management of Uncertainty in Knowledge-Based Systems*, 2016, pp. 36–47.
- [29] B.E. Thompson, Syllogisms using “few”, “many” and “most”, *Notre Dame J. Form. Log.* 23 (1982) 75–84.
- [30] P. Peterson, *Intermediate Quantifiers. Logic, Linguistics, and Aristotelian Semantics*, Ashgate, Aldershot, 2000.
- [31] V. Novák, On fuzzy type theory, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 149 (2005) 235–273.
- [32] R.L.O. Cignoli, I.M.L. D’Ottaviano, D. Mundici, *Algebraic Foundations of Many-Valued Reasoning*, Kluwer, Dordrecht, 2000.
- [33] P. Andrews, *An Introduction to Mathematical Logic and Type Theory: To Truth Through Proof*, Kluwer, Dordrecht, 2002.
- [34] V. Novák, A comprehensive theory of trichotomous evaluative linguistic expressions, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 159 (22) (2008) 2939–2969.
- [35] V. Novák, I. Perfilieva, A. Dvořák, *Insight into Fuzzy Modeling*, Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey, 2016.

- [36] V. Novák, A formal theory of intermediate quantifiers, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 159 (10) (2008) 1229–1246.
- [37] V. Novák, P. Murinová, A formal model of the intermediate quantifiers “A few”, “Several”, “A little”, in: R. Kearfott, I. Batyrshin, M. Reformat, M. Ceberio, V. Kreinovich (Eds.), *Fuzzy Techniques: Theory and Applications*, Springer, Cham, Switzerland, 2019, pp. 429–441.
- [38] P. Murinová, V. Novák, A formal theory of generalized intermediate syllogisms, *Fuzzy Sets Syst.* 186 (2013) 47–80.
- [39] P. Murinová, V. Novák, Logical syllogisms with “almost all, most, many, a few” and “several”, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 175 (2024) 109284.
- [40] I. Perfilieva, V. Novák, From neural networks to fuzzy modeling, in: A. Niemczynowicz, I. Perfilieva, L. Garcia-Raffi, R. Kycia (Eds.), *Complex, Hypercomplex and Fuzzy-Valued Neural Networks New Perspectives and Applications*, CRC Press, Taylor & Francis Group, 2024.
- [41] P. Murinová, S. Boffa, From graded Aristotle’s hexagon to graded Peterson’s hexagon of opposition in fuzzy natural logic, in: *Fuzzy Logic and Technology, and Aggregation Operators*, 2023, pp. 369–380.
- [42] N. Pfeifer, G. Sanfilippo, Probabilistic squares and hexagons of opposition under coherence, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 88 (2017) 282–294.
- [43] S. Boffa, P. Murinová, V. Novák, Graded polygons of opposition in fuzzy formal concept analysis, *Int. J. Approx. Reason.* 132 (2021) 128–153.
- [44] S. Boffa, P. Murinová, V. Novák, P. Ferbas, Graded cubes of opposition in fuzzy formal concept analysis, *Int. J. Approx. Reas.* 145 (2022) 187–209.
- [45] P. Murinová, Graded structures of opposition in fuzzy natural logic, *Log. Univers.* 265 (2020) 495–522.
- [46] P. Murinová, V. Novák, Analysis of the intermediate quantifier “many” in fuzzy natural logic, in: *Proc. Int. Conference IFSA-EUSFLAT 2015*, Atlantis Press, 2015, pp. 1147–1153.